

Rendering Context as Images: Lossy Gist Compression of LLM Input Tokens via Flat Image Billing

Wing Wong Chong*

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Abstract

Commercial LLM APIs bill an input image by its pixel area, not by the amount of text printed on it. We exploit this asymmetry with **pxpipe**, a local proxy that rewrites the bulky, token-dense parts of an agentic coding request (the static system prompt and tool documentation, large tool results, and older conversation history) into compact PNG pages before the request leaves the machine, while keeping recent turns as text. On the author’s production CLAUDE CODE traffic (8,904 compressed requests), this reduces cache-weighted input-token cost by **74% on touched requests** and **70% end-to-end** including uncompressed output, measured against a per-request `count_tokens` counterfactual that removes any turn-count confound. The compression is *lossy by tier*: on the reading model (TABLE 5) it is loss-free at the *gist* tier that agents actually depend on (98/98 on an adversarial recall A/B; 18/18 on state tracking; 100/100 on novel arithmetic; zero confabulation), but *unsafe* for byte-exact strings, where the failure mode is silent confabulation (13/15 on dense 12-char hex recall, and 0/15 on an older, harder haystack). End-to-end task quality is preserved on the configurations we measured: SWE-BENCH Lite resolves 10/10 on both arms at -65% request size, and a harder SWE-BENCH Pro subset resolves 14/19 (ON) vs 15/19 (OFF) with verdicts agreeing on 18/19. We document the renderer geometry, the profitability gate, the measurement methodology, and—unusually—a recorded reversal in which an initial “dead” verdict was overturned once the cost model used realistic content density. We argue text-as-image is a practical *recency-graded gist tier* for agentic workloads, not a lossless store.

1 Introduction

Agentic coding assistants resend a large, slowly-changing context on every turn: a fixed system prompt and tool schema, the growing transcript, and verbatim file reads and command output. This context is overwhelmingly *token-dense*—code, JSON, logs, hashes—where a character costs close to one input token rather than the $\sim 3.5\text{--}4$ typical of English prose.

We observe that providers price an input image by pixel area (Anthropic’s documented rule is $\approx (w \cdot h)/750$ tokens), independent of how many characters are legibly printed on it. A page of dense text therefore has two very different prices depending on whether it is sent as text or as an image of that text. **pxpipe** is a transparent proxy that converts only the parts of a request where the image price wins, behind a per-block profitability gate, and leaves everything else byte-identical.

*Independent. Correspondence: wwchong@gmail.com. Code and receipts: <https://github.com/teamchong/pxpipe>.

Novelty. The idea that an image can carry text densely is not new: concurrent work renders text to images to enlarge a model’s effective context by *training* it to read them [1, 5]. Our contribution is orthogonal and, to our knowledge, unreported: the first *training-free, production-deployed* demonstration that *billing arbitrage*—rendering dense context as images because a commercial API prices images by pixel area, not glyph count—yields large *real cost* savings on a live coding agent, together with a measured *gist-vs-verbatim* safety boundary on a model never trained to read these renders.

Contributions.

1. A deployable system (§3) that compresses LLM input tokens by rendering dense context to PNG pages, with a cache-preserving splice and a per-block break-even gate.
2. A confound-free measurement method (§4): an in-request `count_tokens` probe of the original body gives each request its own counterfactual, so savings are not contaminated by run-to-run agentic variance.
3. Production results (§5.1): -74% touched / -70% end-to-end on real traffic, with an empirically re-grounded per-image cost.
4. A tier characterization (§5.2): loss-free gist recall vs silent verbatim confabulation, bracketed from both sides on TABLE 5.
5. End-to-end task parity evidence (§5.4) on SWE-BENCH.
6. A documented falsification-and-reversal (§6) that isolates how a wrong density assumption inverts the entire economic verdict.

2 Background

Image-token billing. Anthropic bills an input image at roughly $(w \cdot h)/750$ tokens after its standard resize, with a cap. Crucially the count is a function of geometry, not glyph count: a 1568×1568 page costs on the order of 10^3 tokens whether it carries 150 or tens of thousands of characters.

Density of agentic traffic. The economic question is the characters-per-token (cpt) ratio of the content. On the author’s CLAUDE CODE traffic we observe a median around 1.2 cpt ($N=354$) and a mean near 1.9 cpt ($N=391$)—far denser than prose. Text at 1 cpt is roughly $3\times$ more expensive per character than the same content imaged at the densities pxpipe achieves (≈ 3.1 characters per *image* token).

Prompt caching. Providers discount repeated prefixes (cache reads at $0.1\times$, cache writes at $1.25\times$ of base input). Any compressor that disturbs the cacheable prefix can erase its own savings; pxpipe preserves a stable image-bytes prefix so caching keeps working (§3).

3 System

pxpipe intercepts `/v1/messages`, decides per request and per block whether to image, rewrites eligible blocks into image pages, splices them back so the static prefix is preserved, and forwards. It compresses three input block classes, each behind the gate:

```
##### SYSTEM PROMPT #####
The following is the system prompt and tool documentation, rendered as whitespace-minified and reflowed into one dense 1573 x 1248 image (~2.7k image tokens), with the OCR instruction banner co-rendered on top and ← marking original newlines. This is what the model receives instead of the text.

1. the static system prompt + tool-documentation slab;
2. large tool_result bodies (file reads, command output, logs) above a ~6k dense-character floor;
3. older collapsed history; recent turns always stay text.

Everything else—user messages, recent turns, sparse prose, the model’s output, and any request on a non-supported model—passes through byte-identical.

Render geometry. Pages use a fixed 5 x 5 px1 monospace atlas at 313 columns, giving a fixed canvas width of 1573 px; height grows with line count and is capped at 1568 px (195 lines), beyond which content pages into additional images. A reflow pass packs content into full-width rows (marking original newlines with a sentinel glyph) so dense pages reach ≈ 50k chars (Figure 1).

1Cell is 5 px wide x 8 px tall (“5x8 cell”).
```

Figure 1: A page produced by the real pipeline: ~48k characters of system prompt and tool documentation (≈25k text tokens) whitespace-minified and reflowed into one dense 1573 × 1248 image (≈2.7k image tokens), with the OCR instruction banner co-rendered on top and ← marking original newlines. This is what the model receives instead of the text.

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Notably, a width-shrink-to-content variant was implemented and reverted within two days: for the dense content the gate admits, reflow already fills the width, so shrinking added gate-prediction complexity for no real-world gain. Full geometry and its commit history are documented with the system.

Profitability gate. For each candidate block the gate compares the predicted image-token cost against the text-token cost at the measured cpt and images only when the image is cheaper. A fixed canvas width makes this prediction exact. Sparse/short-line content never clears the gate and stays text.

Model scope. The transform is enabled only for FABLE 5 (§5.2 motivates this); other models pass through untouched.

4 Measurement methodology

For every `/v1/messages` POST the proxy issues, in parallel with the real (compressed) forward, a free `count_tokens` probe on the *original, pre-compression* body, and records the provider’s actually-billed `usage` from the response. Both land in one row of an append-only event log. Because the counterfactual is computed from the same request at the same moment, there is no turn-count or run-to-run confound: each request is its own control.

We convert tokens to a cache-weighted input-equivalent using list ratios (input $\times 1.0$, cache-write $\times 1.25$, cache-read $\times 0.1$, output $\times 5.0$), applying cache pricing identically to both sides so the caching discount cancels. The counterfactual is cache-aware: on a warm turn the unproxied path is also warm, so its cache buckets are modeled rather than collapsed to a single weight (a naive single-weight baseline understates warm-turn cost and was corrected).

5 Results

5.1 Economics on production traffic

Over the author’s event log restricted to successful POSTs (9,791 requests; 8,904 compressed, 887 passed through), the cache-weighted input-equivalent falls as in Table 1. An earlier, larger snapshot (13,709 requests) reported -59% end-to-end / -72% touched (a \$100 bill $\rightarrow \sim \$41$); the two snapshots differ in composition, and we report both rather than the more favorable one.

Table 1: Production input-equivalent savings (cache-weighted).

slice	baseline	actual	reduction
touched (compressed)	1.035×10^9	2.690×10^8	-74%
all POSTs (incl. untouched)	1.050×10^9	2.842×10^8	-73%
end-to-end (incl. output $\times 5$)	1.094×10^9	3.279×10^8	-70%

Per-image cost, re-grounded. A two-variable regression on cold-miss events ($N \approx 1.5\text{k}$), $\text{tokens} \approx a \cdot \text{text_chars} + b \cdot \text{image_pixels}$, yields ≈ 1.8 chars/token for text and ≈ 907 pixels/token

for images—close to the documented $(w \cdot h)/750$, and notably cheaper than a stale internal constant (~ 2500 tok/image) the gate still assumes. The gate is therefore likely conservative on current traffic; a fit from the event log should replace the constant.

5.2 Reading fidelity (gist tier)

On FABLE 5, rendered pages read at parity with text on the gist tier that agents depend on (Table 2). FABLE 5 also removed the $\sim 7\%$ read tax that OPUS 4.8 incurred on the same renders, motivating the Fable-only scope; image billing is unchanged because Fable ships the same tokenizer line.

Table 2: Reading-fidelity evals on FABLE 5 (text vs imaged). Higher is better except confabulation (lower is better).

eval	N /arm	text	imaged
novel arithmetic	100	100%	100% (-38% tok)
gist recall (decisions/values/paths/names/negation, w/ distractors)	98	98/98	98/98
state tracking (value mutated $3\times$; final/first/count)	18	18/18	18/18
confabulation on never-stated facts	16	0/16	0/16

5.3 The verbatim limit

Byte-exact recovery of random strings is the hard case and the documented failure boundary. On dense 12-char hex recall FABLE 5 scores **13/15** and OPUS **0/15** on an older, denser haystack; both misses are *single-glyph silent confabulations* on visually adjacent digits (e.g. $3 \rightarrow 9$, $8 \rightarrow 0$), returned confidently with no error signal. A controlled font-size sweep (§6) shows the cause is pixels-per-glyph (resolution), not an encoder that is “hex-blind”—large, sparse glyphs read at 100%. Consequence: anything that must round-trip byte-exact (IDs, hashes, secrets, exact numbers) must stay text. Recent turns do; a dedicated verbatim-risk guard in the gate is identified but not yet built.

5.4 End-to-end task quality

We test whether imaging old context degrades task completion, using the official SWEBENCH Docker harness and paired ON/OFF runs whose arms are pinned to separate proxy ports in-process (so the operator’s shell environment cannot leak into either arm).

Table 3: SWE-BENCH task quality (Claude Code + FABLE 5).

	pxpipe ON	OFF
Lite (resolved)	10/10	10/10
Lite (request size vs own body)	-65%	± 0
Pro (resolved, $n=19$)	14/19	15/19
Pro (request size vs own body)	-60%	± 0

On Pro, verdicts agree on 18/19; the single split (one ON failure) re-resolved 3/3 when replicated, indicating run-to-run agentic variance rather than a compression effect. Samples are small

and Lite skews easy; we read this as *parity evidence*, not superiority.

6 A documented reversal

We preserve, rather than rewrite, an initial postmortem that declared the approach “dead.” That verdict rested on three errors worth naming because they are the ones a reader is most likely to repeat:

1. **Wrong cost model.** The break-even math used English-prose density (~ 3.5 cpt), where images lose. Real traffic is $\sim 1\text{--}1.9$ cpt, where they win by $\sim 3\times$. A font-size sweep at prose density showed the readable zone (≤ 22 pt, ~ 4.4 k chars/page, 100% read) and the cheap zone (≥ 16 pt) are anti-correlated—*at prose density*. At realistic density the same readable page already wins.
2. **Worst-case generalization.** Concluding the product was dead from the single hardest sub-task (random-hex verbatim) conflated a real limitation with overall utility.
3. **Unverified assumption.** The analysis assumed the interactive session bypassed the proxy; the event log showed it did not.

The corrected verdict: the encoder limit kills *verbatim*; it does not kill a *gist* tier on dense traffic. We include this section because the failure mode of this entire idea is an unexamined density assumption, and showing the inversion explicitly is more useful than a clean narrative.

7 Limitations and threats to validity

Lossy. Verbatim recall from images is unreliable and fails silently; the verbatim-risk guard is not yet built. **Small n .** The SWE-BENCH Pro sample is 19 pairs and Lite is 10; both warrant scaling. **Single operator.** The production economics come from one author’s event log; cpt and savings are workload-dependent and lose money on sparse prose. **Model scope.** Results are FABLE 5-specific; the read tax differs across models. **Billing constant.** The internal per-image cost constant disagrees with a fresh regression by $\sim 3\times$ and should be re-grounded. **Latency.** Rendering adds time before a large request leaves, partly offset by fewer ingested tokens.

8 Related work

Visual-text / optical context compression (closest). The core intuition—that rendering text as an image packs more content per vision token than per text token—is shared with recent work. DeepSeek-OCR studies “contexts optical compression” [5], and Glyph scales context windows via visual-text compression [1]. Both *adapt or train the model* to read visually-compressed context, and target *capability* (longer effective context, model throughput). ppipe differs on every axis that matters for deployment: (i) it is a *drop-in proxy on a frozen commercial API*, requiring no model training or weights access; (ii) it targets *cost* under a specific real billing rule (flat image pricing) rather than context-window capacity; (iii) it reports *production economics* with a per-request counterfactual on real agentic traffic; and (iv) it characterizes a concrete *gist-vs-verbatim safety boundary* (with a silent-confabulation failure mode) on a model not trained to read these renders. In short, prior work makes a model read images of text; ppipe makes an *existing* model’s *bill* smaller and measures what that costs in fidelity.

Prompt / context compression broadly. Token pruning and paraphrastic compression (e.g. LLMingua-style methods) [2], learned soft prompts and gist tokens that distill instructions into few tokens [4], and retrieval that avoids resending context [3] all *rewrite or shrink* the content. pxpipe is orthogonal: it changes the *billing modality* of otherwise byte-unchanged context, trading exact-byte fidelity for a flat image price. A controlled head-to-head against LLMingua, and against Glyph/DeepSeek-OCR on matched dense inputs, is left to future work.

9 Conclusion

Billing context as images is a practical, recency-graded *gist* tier for agentic LLM workloads: $\sim 70\%$ measured input-cost reduction on real traffic, loss-free gist recall on the reading model, task parity in what we measured, and a clearly bounded verbatim hazard. The open work is a verbatim-risk guard, a re-grounded cost gate, larger task-quality samples, and testing whether imaged bulk also enlarges *effective* context (more usable content per token window), not just the bill.

Reproducibility

System, evals, harnesses, and per-request receipts are open at <https://github.com/teamchong/pxpipe> (see `eval/`, `FINDINGS.md`, `docs/RENDER_SIZING.md`). Production economics are reproducible from the proxy’s event log with the published cache-aware formula.

References

- [1] Jiale Cheng, Yusen Liu, Xinyu Zhang, Yulin Fei, Wenyi Hong, Ruiliang Lyu, Weihang Wang, Zhe Su, Xiaotao Gu, Xiao Liu, Yushi Bai, Jie Tang, Hongning Wang, and Minlie Huang. Glyph: Scaling context windows via visual-text compression. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.17800*, 2025.
- [2] Huiqiang Jiang, Qianhui Wu, Chin-Yew Lin, Yuqing Yang, and Lili Qiu. LLMingua: Compressing prompts for accelerated inference of large language models. In *Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, pages 13358–13376, 2023.
- [3] Patrick Lewis, Ethan Perez, Aleksandra Piktus, Fabio Petroni, Vladimir Karpukhin, Naman Goyal, Heinrich Küttler, Mike Lewis, Wen-tau Yih, Tim Rocktäschel, Sebastian Riedel, and Douwe Kiela. Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive NLP tasks. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2020.
- [4] Jesse Mu, Xiang Lisa Li, and Noah Goodman. Learning to compress prompts with gist tokens. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2023.
- [5] Haoran Wei, Yaofeng Sun, and Yukun Li. DeepSeek-OCR: Contexts optical compression. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.18234*, 2025.